

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Perception and Propensities of Senior High School (SHS) students towards teaching profession: Basis for recommendations in promoting education Majorship for all SHS Strands

Linda Cangayao * and Dennis Gamad Caballes

School of Teacher Education, National Teachers College, Manila, Philippines.

World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2023, 17(02), 275–286

Publication history: Received on 17 December 2022; revised on 07 February 2023; accepted on 09 February 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2023.17.2.0179>

Abstract

The purpose of the study is to investigate the perception and propensities of Senior High School (SHS) students regarding the teaching profession. Convergent Mixed Method research design will be used in this study since the data will be collected at the same time through a consolidated survey instrument, analyzed separately, and then compared to have complete understanding of the research problem (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The respondents of the study are SHS students of the National Teachers College. Stratified sampling was employed ensuring that all strands are well-represented. The consolidated survey instrument will collect the demographic profile of the respondents, RIASEC Career Pathway test, researcher-made test on propensities to perform the duties and responsibilities and the open-ended questions on their perception about teaching profession. Research instruments used in this study have sound psychometric properties. The data will be analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation to know the level of career pathway, and propensity to become a teacher. The impact of SHS strands and career pathway were gauged through Kruskal Wallis H test with epsilon square calculation for the effect size. Spearman Rank Order Correlation was used to know the significant relationship between career pathway and propensities to perform duties and responsibilities of teachers. Thematic analysis was employed to interpret the perception of respondents regarding the teaching profession.

Keywords: Teacher Education; Senior High School; Career Pathway; RIASEC; Education Degree

1. Introduction

According to Statistics from the website of Commission of Higher Education (CHED) of the Philippines posted in 2020, Business Administration and Related Courses consistently hailed as the most populated course from 2009 to 2020. As prescribed in the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, in June 2016 DepEd launched senior high school (SHS) nationwide, a new level of basic education consisting of grades 11 and 12 (*Implementing the Senior High School Support Program, 2022*) producing its first graduate in 2018. No significant differences were noted in the ranking of most populated courses as Education remained top two (2) from 2010 to 2020 despite the implementation of SHS in 2016. This confirmed that even before the implementation of SHS, high school completers had great inclination towards business related courses.

Producing graduates from business related courses will surely help boost our economy however, the Philippines is battling a far more wide and dangerous battle and that is the crisis in education. Chanco (2022) mentioned in his business section in *Philstar Global* that the World Bank reported that the learning poverty in the Philippines pre-pandemic was already at 90.9 percent. It also noted “the share of children at the end of primary (elementary), who read below the minimum proficiency level,” was also a high of 90.4 percent. This has been confirmed by the 2018 PISA report

* Corresponding author: Linda Cangayao

wherein the global survey revealed that out of 79 countries, the Philippines ranked lowest in Reading Comprehension and second lowest in both Science and Mathematics (Gatchalian, 2020). Senator Win Gatchalian, who is the Committee Chair for Basic Education believes that one of the ways to alleviate this crisis is through improving the quality of teacher education and by providing professional development opportunities.

Despite this alarming reality, Alliance of Concerned Teachers (ACT) implied that we are having a teacher shortage and according to them there is a need to hire 147, 000 new teachers to lower class size and improve the quality of learning. In fact, according to Dana Beltran, ACT deputy secretary general, we need P54 billion as a worthy investment for our youth's and nation's future. However, the truth is because of the poor teaching condition, this figure could be worse as yearly, many teachers exit service and seek better paying jobs (Mendoza, 2022).

Indubitably, the government is seeing the value of education in building the nation thus, putting in place policies that will make this profession attractive to the younger generation. Meanwhile, there is also a need for teacher education training schools to craft programs that will encourage SHS completers to take on the challenges of becoming a soldier than will fight the crisis on education and regardless of their strands, there will be an appropriate majorship for them to take.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The goal of this study is to uncover the propensity and perception of SHS students towards becoming a teacher. Specifically, it yields to answer the following questions:

- What is the career pathway of the respondents based on RIASEC?
- What is the level of propensity of the respondents to perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher?
- Is there a significant difference in the propensity of the respondents to perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher?
- Is there a significant difference in the propensity of the respondents to perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher?
- Does strand have an impact on career pathways and propensities to perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher?
- What is the perception of the respondents regarding the teaching profession?

1.2. Related Studies

1.2.1. College Courses and Senior High School Career Tracks

The article of Official Gazette of the government entitled *The K to 12 Basic Education Program* mentioned that Senior High School covers eight learning areas as part of its core curriculum, and adds specific tracks (similar to college courses) based on four disciplines:

- Academic (which includes Business, Science & Engineering, Humanities & Social Science, and a General Academic strand)
- Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (with highly specialized subjects with TESDA qualifications)
- Sports
- Arts & Design

It was implemented because a 13-year basic education program is a recognized standard for students and professionals globally. In addition, the Philippines is the last country in Asia and one of the only three (3) countries worldwide. Most journal articles and publications materials related to senior high school were mainly about the list of specialized subjects and steps on how to choose appropriate strands; however, there were no specific guidelines on how SHS students can choose appropriate college degrees or majors. This could be due to the fact that most strands appropriate college majors are straightforward. Consistent in two (2) websites namely courses.com.ph and CIIT (College of Arts and Technology), Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) and Elementary Education (BEED) are recommended for General Academic Strand (GAS) but never for STEM, HUMMS and ABM graduates. In this study, the researchers will attempt to come up with recommendations of college education majors that will match the four (4) disciplines of SHS.

1.2.2. Career Pathway by RIASEC

John Holland (1992) expressed that individuals are attracted to a particular career because it matches their personalities and other variables related to their backgrounds. The key concept behind his theory is that career choices

are primarily motivated by looking for a work environment that will allow them to use their gifts and talents; thus, behavior is determined by interaction between personality and environment. According to Zunker (2016), Holland proposed that personality types can be arranged in a coded system (RIASEC theory) following his modal-personal-orientation themes such as R (realistic occupation); I (investigative); A (artistic); S (social); E (enterprising); and C (conventional). The Career and Technical Education section of Hawai'i State Department of Education provided a copy of the RIASEC in a simple, comprehensible and easy to score version of the RIASEC test. It has 42 statements wherein students need to fill in the circle of the statements they agree on. Afterwards, scores need to be added up per column to get the total. The letters/codes with the highest scores are the respondent's *Interest Code*. Below are the interpretations of the *Career Pathways* based on codes:

Table 1 RIASEC Code, Characteristics and Related Pathways

RIASEC Code	Characteristics	Related Pathways
R-Realistic	These people are often good at mechanical or athletic jobs. Good college majors for Realistic people are Agriculture, Health Assistant, Computers, Construction, Mechanic/Machinist, Engineering, Food and Hospitality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural Resources • Health Services • Industrial and Engineering Technology • Arts and Communication
I= Investigative	These people like to watch, learn, analyze and solve problems. Good college majors for Investigative people are Marine Biology, Engineering, Chemistry, Zoology, Medicine/Surgery, Consumer Economics, Psychology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Services • Business Public • Human Services • Industrial and Engineering Technology
A = Artistic	These people like to work in unstructured situations where they can use their creativity. Good majors for Artistic people are Communications, Cosmetology, Fine and Performing Arts, Photography, Radio and TV, Interior Design, Architecture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and Human Services • Arts and Communication
S = Social	These people like to work with other people, rather than things. Good college majors for Social people are Counseling, Nursing, Physical Therapy, Travel, Advertising, Public Relations, Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public and Human Services • Arts and Communication
E= Enterprising	These people like to work with others and enjoy persuading and performing. Good college majors for Enterprising people are: Fashion Merchandising, Real Estate, Marketing/Sales, Law, Political Science, International Trade, Banking/Finance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business • Public and Human Services • Arts and Communication
C= Conventional	These people are very detail oriented, organized and like to work with data. Good college majors for Conventional people are Accounting , Court Reporting , Insurance , Administration , Medical Records , Banking , Data Processing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health Services • Business • Industrial and Engineering Technology

Swanson (2018) in his study discovered that the RIASEC profiles of foreign language teachers were Social, Artistic and Enterprising (SAE). He also indicated that Holland's theory grouped teachers in the Social domain wherein they are described as someone who prefers activities that involve working with people that educate, inform, cure, or enlighten and are characterized by people who enjoy helping others and engaging in social activities.

In this study, RIASEC will be used in a different light wherein it will be instrumental in determining if the career pathway of Senior High School students and if it would match their chosen strands and if they have propensities to become a teacher.

1.2.3. Standards, Duties and Responsibilities of a Teacher

International Teaching Certification has five (5) standards for globally competent teacher that is (1) being familiar with the characteristics of education in an international context, (2) being familiar with wide variety of strategies and methods for teaching culturally diverse student, (3) understands how to facilitate a learning environment that meets the needs of students, (4) recognises the challenges and opportunities of teaching a transient or mobile student population, and a reflective practitioner.

Similarly, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST) posits that effective teachers (1) recognize the importance of the mastery of content knowledge, (2) provides learning environments that are fair and supportive in order to promote learner responsibility and achievement, (3) establish learning environments that are responsive to learner diversity, (4) interact with the national and local curriculum requirements, (5) apply a variety of assessment tools and strategies in monitoring, evaluating, documenting and reporting learners' needs, progress and achievement, (6) establish school-community partnerships aimed at enriching the learning environment, as well as the community's engagement in the educative process and lastly, (7) someone who value personal growth and professional development and exhibit high personal regard for the profession.

Congruence was observed in the local and international standards of an effective and competent teacher. Nevertheless, below are the expected duties and responsibilities of teachers according to the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) from Department of Education:

- Teaches or more grades/levels using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies
- Facilitates learning in the elementary/secondary schools through functional lesson plans (for new teachers up to 3 years) daily Log (for teachers teaching 4 years and above) of activities and appropriate, adequate, and updated instructional materials.
- Monitors and evaluates pupils/students' progress
- Undertakes activities to improve performance indicators
- Maintains updated pupils/students' progress regularly.
- Supervises curricular and co-curricular projects and activities
- Maintains updated pupil/student school records
- Counsels and guides pupils/students
- Supports activities of governmental and non-governmental organizations
- Conducts Action Plan
- Maintains Daily Routine (classroom cleanliness, classroom management, overall physical classroom atmosphere)
- Maintains harmonious relationship with fellow teachers and other school personnel as well as with parents and other stakeholders

These duties and responsibilities will be transformed into statements wherein the extent of endorsement of the Senior High School Students will be measured. This can be correlated with the scores of the respondents in the RIASEC items under Social Codes (4, 12, 13, 20, 28, 34 and 40).

2. Methods

Convergent Mixed Method research design was employed in this study since the data were collected at the same time through a consolidated survey instrument, analyzed separately, and then compared to have complete understanding of the research problem (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The respondents were the SHS students of the National Teachers College. The consolidated survey instrument was used to collect the demographic profile of the respondents, RIASEC Career Pathway test, researcher-made test on propensities to become a teacher and the open-ended questions on their perception about teaching profession. This research instrument underwent reliability and validity testing. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation and rank to interpret the demographic profile, career pathway, and propensity to become a teacher. Non-parametric statistical analysis was used because the data violates the assumptions of the parametric test. Kruskal wallis H test was used to calculate for the significant difference based on strands coupled with epsilon square for effect size calculation. Spearman rank order correlation was used to measure the significant relationship between career pathways and propensities to perform the

duties and responsibilities of a teacher. Thematic analysis was likewise employed to interpret the perception of respondents regarding the teaching profession.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Career pathway of the SHS respondents based on RIASEC when grouped according to strands specifically to codes related to Education

Table 2 Career Pathway per SHS Strand

Strand		Career Pathway					
		Realistic	Investigative	Artistic	Social	Enterprising	Conventional
ABM	Mean	4.76	4.09	3.58	4.64	4.20	5.60
	N	45	45	45	45	45	45
	SD	1.46	1.55	1.62	1.23	1.36	1.45
HUMMS	Mean	5.28	4.00	4.64	5.00	4.00	5.76
	N	25	25	25	25	25	25
	SD	1.54	1.76	1.44	1.04	1.68	1.42
ICT	Mean	4.82	4.23	3.70	4.43	3.61	5.38
	N	79	79	79	79	79	79
	SD	1.45	1.47	1.85	1.40	1.61	1.43
STEM	Mean	4.86	4.54	3.81	4.57	3.89	5.32
	N	150	150	150	150	150	150
	SD	1.44	1.66	1.69	1.25	1.41	1.48
Total	Mean	4.87	4.34	3.82	4.58	3.87	5.41
	N	299	299	299	299	299	299
	SD	1.45	1.61	1.72	1.28	1.49	1.46

Data analysis revealed that most students have inclination on activities related to Conventional Pathway ($M=5.41$, $SD=1.46$) followed by Realistic, Social, Investigative while the least are Enterprising and Artistic. This implies that the majority are very detail oriented, organized and like to work with data. This correlates with the least scored career pathway which is Artistic as they are described as unstructured situations where they can use their creativity. Being an educator falls under the SAE (Social, Artistic, and Entrepreneurship) career codes which contains the least two (2) of the least endorsed career pathways of respondents. This means that while most students like to work with other people, rather than things, they may have challenges with working in unstructured situations where they can use their creativity and in work with others and enjoy persuading and performing.

HUMMS have the highest average in terms of career codes SAE (Social, Artistic, and Investigative) which means they may have the qualities needed to become a teacher followed by STEM then ICT while ABM had the least because of the low score in being Investigative and Entrepreneurship.

3.2. Level of propensity of the respondents to perform the tasks of teachers when grouped according to strands

Data revealed that the respondents see themselves performing the duties and responsibilities of teachers to an average extent ($M=2.84$, $SD=.69$). SHS respondents of this study rated themselves the highest in terms of their capability to maintain harmonious relationships with fellow teachers and other school personnel as well as with parents and other stakeholders ($M=3.05$, $SD=0.90$). This is followed by conducting action plans ($M=3.00$, $SD=.84$), supporting government and non-government activities ($M=3.00$, $SD=.92$) and maintaining a daily routine ($M=3.00$, $SD=0.92$).

Table 3 Propensities to Perform Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers based on Strand

Statements	ABM		HUMMS		ICT		STEM		Total	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
I see myself teaching or handling more grades/levels using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies.	2.60	0.98	2.81	1.02	2.31	1.07	2.37	1.03	2.47	1.04
I see myself facilitating learning.	2.79	0.90	3.04	0.77	2.53	1.05	2.85	0.88	2.78	0.93
I see myself monitoring and evaluating pupils/students' progress.	2.75	0.93	3.04	0.77	2.55	1.01	2.71	1.02	2.72	0.97
I see myself undertaking the activities to improve performance indicators.	3.17	0.72	3.19	0.80	2.73	0.96	2.96	0.95	2.98	0.90
I see myself maintaining and updating pupils/students' progress regularly.	2.88	0.94	2.92	0.89	2.53	1.03	2.81	0.95	2.77	0.97
I see myself supervising curricular and co-curricular projects and activities.	2.88	0.87	2.92	0.85	2.47	0.99	2.86	0.83	2.77	0.89
I see myself maintaining updated pupil/student school records.	2.81	0.98	2.81	0.94	2.45	1.05	2.79	1.02	2.71	1.01
I see myself counseling and guiding pupils/students.	2.77	0.91	3.04	0.77	2.53	0.97	2.83	1.00	2.77	0.95
I see myself supporting activities of governmental and non-governmental organizations.	3.08	0.79	3.19	0.63	2.76	0.99	3.04	1.01	3.00	0.92
I see myself conducting action plans.	2.98	0.73	3.12	0.82	2.78	0.97	3.13	0.81	3.00	0.84
I see myself maintaining daily routing such as classroom cleanliness, classroom management, overall physical classroom atmosphere.	3.04	0.87	2.96	0.92	2.90	1.01	3.06	0.89	3.00	0.92
I see myself maintaining a harmonious relationship with fellow teachers and other school personnel as well as with parents and other stakeholders. .	3.04	0.87	3.12	0.77	2.90	0.96	3.13	0.92	3.05	0.90
Total	2.90	0.64	3.01	0.51	2.62	0.77	2.88	0.70	2.84	0.69

Legend: 1.00-1.75 (Not at all), 1.76-2.50 (Poor Extent), 2.51-3.25 (Average Extent), 3.26-4.00 (Great extent)

On the other hand, they seemed to be least confident in terms of seeing themselves teaching or handling more grades/levels using appropriate and innovative teaching strategies (M=2.47, SD=1.04) as well as maintaining updated

pupil/student school records (M=2.71, SD=1.01) and monitoring and evaluating pupils/students’ progress (M=2.72, SD=0.97).

The strand with the highest propensity to perform the duties and responsibilities of teachers are STEM students with above average mean score of 3.13 and standard deviation of .92. HUMMS students ranked second (M=3.12, SD=.77) followed by ABM (M=3.04, SD=.87) while ICT ranked the lowest with 2.90 mean score and .96 standard deviation.

3.3. Significant Impact of Strands to Career Pathways and the Propensities to Perform the Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers

Kruskal Wallis H test was used to gauge the significant difference between the career pathways and the propensities to perform the duties and responsibilities of teachers. The statistical analysis is deemed appropriate because the data is not normally distributed based on the Shapiro Wilk test. Significant impact was gauged through effect size calculation via epsilon square.

Table 4 Significant Difference and Effect of SHS Strand to Career Pathway and Propensities to Perform Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers based on Strand

	Realistic	Investigative	Artistic	Social	Enterprising	Conventional	PDRT
Kruskal-Wallis H	2.896	6.159	6.732	3.427	4.403	3.142	4.391
df	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Asymp. Sig.	.408	.104	.081	.330	.221	.370	.222
Effect Size	0.010	0.021	0.023	0.012	0.015	0.011	0.015

Legend: PDRT (Propensities to perform the Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers), df (degrees of freedom), Asymp. Sig. (p value)

No significant difference was found in terms of the career pathway and the propensities to perform the duties and responsibilities of teachers (p>.05). The effect size value obtained via epsilon square ranged from .010 to 0.023 which indicates a weak effect based on the interpretation of r by Rea and Parker (1992). This implies that despite the noted differences in terms of career pathways and propensities to perform duties and responsibilities of a teacher based on strands, it can be deduced that SHS students are of the same level or range in terms of the variables being explored in this study.

3.4. Relationship of Career Codes and Propensities to Perform Duties and Responsibilities of a Teacher

Spearman-Rho rank was used to explore the correlation between career codes because the data set violated assumptions of linearity, homoscedasticity, and normality.

Table 5 Correlation of Career Codes and Propensities to Perform Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers

			Realistic	Investigative	Artistic	Social	Enterprising	Conventional	PDRT
Spearman's rho	Realistic	Correlation Coefficient	1	0.279**	0.307**	0.331**	0.340**	0.280**	0.169**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.003
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299
	Investigative	Correlation Coefficient	0.279**	1	0.283**	0.299**	0.191**	0.322**	0.112
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.001	0.00	0.053
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299
	Artistic	Correlation Coefficient	0.307**	0.283**	1	0.431**	0.337**	0.211**	0.229**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299

	Social	Correlation Coefficient	0.331**	0.299**	0.431**	1	0.385**	0.207**	0.215**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299	299
	Enterprising	Correlation Coefficient	0.340**	0.191**	0.337**	0.385**	1	0.287**	0.281**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.001	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299	
	Conventional	Correlation Coefficient	0.280**	0.322**	0.211**	0.207**	0.287**	1	0.160**	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.005	
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299	
	PDRT	Correlation Coefficient	0.169**	0.112	0.229**	0.215**	0.281**	0.160**	1	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	0.003	0.053	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.005	0.00	
		N	299	299	299	299	299	299	299	

Legend: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); PDRT (Propensities to perform Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers); Interpretation: $\leq .29$ = Weak Correlation, $\leq .49$ = Moderate Correlation, $\geq .50$ = Strong Correlation

There is a positive and weak correlation between variables. This implies that when the scores in Career Pathways such as Realistic, Investigative, Artistic, Social, Enterprising and Conventional increases, the Propensity to perform the duties and responsibilities of teachers increases as well but to a weak and almost negligible extent only. To calculate for the effect size, coefficient of determination was used by simply squaring the r value and it shows that the range of shared variance was from 1% to 8%. Surprisingly, Enterprising has the highest shared variance of 8% compared to Social Career Pathway (5%) while Investigative has the lowest shared variance.

3.5. Perception of the respondents regarding the teaching profession

Table 6 SHS Inclination to become a teacher based on the Average Scores in SAE Teacher RIASEC Code

Responses	Average Score in Social, Artistic and Entrepreneurship Course Codes			
	Above Average	Average	Below Average	Grand Total
No	20	219	33	272
ABM	2	34	5	41
HUMMS	3	14	1	18
ICT	5	57	13	75
STEM	10	114	14	138
Yes	3	20	4	27
ABM		4		4
HUMMS		6	1	7
ICT	1	1	2	4
STEM	2	9	1	12
Grand Total	23	239	37	299

91% of the SHS who responded in this study shared that they do not like to become teachers. Their response was compared with the average scores in Career Pathways codes related to Teaching Profession, which is Social, Artistic and Investigative (SAE) and in their propensity to perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher.

Table 7 SHS Inclination to become a teacher based on the Average Scores in Propensities to Perform Duties and Responsibilities of Teachers

Propensities to Perform the Duties and Responsibilities of a Teacher					
Responses	Great Extent	Moderate Extent	Poor Extent	Not at all	Total
No	63	130	50	29	272
ABM	10	22	6	3	41
HUMMS	4	11	2	1	18
ICT	9	39	17	10	75
STEM	40	58	25	15	138
Yes	12	14	1		27
ABM	3	1			4
HUMMS	2	5			7
ICT	3	1			4
STEM	4	7	1		12
Grand Total	75	144	51	29	299

Table 8 Perception of SHS respondents toward the Teaching Profession

Themes of Responses		ABM	HUMMS	ICT	STEM	OVERALL
Positive	f	25	21	51	80	177
	%	56%	84%	65%	53%	59%
<i>Noble/good/honorable/great/lovely profession</i>		5	5	19	15	43
<i>Good career</i>		2		1	3	16
<i>Fun</i>		3	1	2	6	12
<i>Not for me</i>		1		5	8	4
<i>Enticing/interesting</i>		1	1		2	4
<i>Crucial/needed</i>			1	1	1	3
<i>Creates lesson plan</i>			2		1	3
<i>Helps students achieve goals/learning outcomes</i>			1	1	1	3
Negative	f	21	9	27	66	123
	%	47%	36%	34%	44%	41%
<i>Hard/difficult/challenging</i>		12	3	11	33	59
<i>Needs patience</i>		3	3	2	7	15
<i>Stressful</i>		1			6	7
<i>Small salary/ underpaid</i>		1		2	1	4

It is understandable for the 33 students who have below average scores in terms of Social, Artistic, and Investigative average scores however, 239 students who have average (n=219) and above average (n=20) scores in SAE course codes also expressed dislike to become a teacher. Those who want to become teachers have average SAE scores (n=20) followed by those with below average scores (n=4). Only three (3) who are above average want to become a teacher.

The same is true in terms of the propensities in performing duties and responsibilities of a teacher wherein 70% of SHS students who shared they do not like to become teachers expressed that they can perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher to a moderate and great extent. 30% of those who said no were understandable because their scores signaled that they can only perform teachers' duties and responsibilities to a poor extent or not at all. Those who answered yes obtained scores showing that they can do the task of the teachers to a moderate and even to a great extent.

To better understand the perception of students regarding the teaching profession, thematic analysis was employed to the qualitative data. Analysis revealed that more than half of the respondents have positive perception towards the teaching profession and see it as noble, good, honorable, fun, enticing/interesting, needed, and helpful; however, some of the students who have positive perception see this as not suitable for them. 41% have negative perceptions towards the teaching profession because they see it as a hard, difficult or challenging profession. They see it as a job that needs a lot of patience, stressful, and underpaid.

4. Conclusion

This present study explored the propensities and perception of SHS students towards the teaching profession. Overall, the data showed the following:

- SHS students are mostly clustered under Conventional career pathway which implies that they tend to become very detail oriented, organized and like to work with data.
- Being an educator falls under the SAE (Social, Artistic, and Investigative) career codes which contains the two (2) of the least endorsed career pathways of respondents. Majority of the participants may like to work with other people, rather than things but they may have difficulty with watching, learning, analyzing, and solving problems as well as working in unstructured situations where they can use their creativity.
- Participants have the propensity to perform the duties and responsibilities of a teacher to an average extent. SHS students are confident in establishing harmonious relationships with all stakeholders but find teaching strategies, updating, monitoring and evaluating teacher records challenging.
- No significant difference was found in the career pathways and propensities to perform duties and responsibilities of teachers thus, SHS strands do not impact the two (2) variables.
- No significant correlations were found between career pathways and propensities as well. This implies that these two (2) are independent from each other.
- 91% of the students do not like to become teachers despite having high scores in Career Pathway codes in teaching which is Social, Artistic and Entrepreneurship. Those who do not like to become teachers obtained good scores in propensities to perform the duties and responsibilities to become a teacher.
- Overall students have positive perception towards the teaching profession but they do not see it as a viable profession since it is deemed as challenging, stressful, and undercompensated.

Today more than ever, there is a need to promote the teaching profession to help a country that is education poor. Despite this saddening reality, we are facing another challenge of making this profession enticing to incoming college students. It appears that based on their career codes many of them are profiled to another career pathway which means their interests are inclined to other professions to begin with.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research and supported by prior studies, the following are recommended for the school administrators, faculty, guidance office and all concerned offices:

- School of Teachers Education should introduce Educational Career Pathways based on strands or career pathways such as STEM, ABM and ICT students may take BSED Science, BSED Math, BPED or BTLED. HUMMS students may consider BSED Social Studies, BSED English, or BSED Filipino.
- Educational Ladderized Program can be introduced to students who opt to take non-educational courses in NTC but has high propensity to become teachers wherein professional education subjects can be taken during summer or the summer immediately after graduation.
-

- Students who have high scores in career codes related to teaching and/or propensities to perform duties and responsibilities of teachers should be invited for a special training and immersion to *School of Teacher Education* to unleash their potential, further equip them with the needed teacher training and alleviate their apprehension towards the teaching profession.
- In coordination with the Guidance Office, Career Talks should be conducted wherein successful non-teacher and teacher education graduates can share about their efficient strategies making teaching a joyful and rewarding experience rather than plainly seeing it as hard or challenging. Financial and other perks of being in the teaching profession should also be tackled as long as new ways of efficiently handling teaching tasks will alleviate the issues on the teaching as a very difficult, underpaid and underappreciated profession.

Future Work

The study was based on a limited number of students as pointed out in the preceding discussions. It would be of more significance if a future study will be extended to a larger population to better understand the characteristics of Senior High School students based on career pathways and their propensities and perception regarding the teaching profession. Although these results may not lead to conclusions about the variables under study, they shed some light on an extremely important topic about how SHS students perceive the teaching profession.

Moreover, a follow-up or cohort study could be conducted after the implementation of a symposium on the results of the study and addressing concerns or issues raised pertaining to the teaching profession.

Taking into account the aforementioned recommendations, further studies/evaluation of students' performance may be facilitated to find out if there are improvements that transpired. The school administrators, faculty and other concerned offices are also encouraged to instigate with their own respective studies to further validate the results of this research.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to thank the Research Director of NTC, Prof. Ronalyn Federizo, the Principal of the Senior High School Department, Mr. Fidel Soriano and the Academic Coordinator of the said department, Ms. Princess Hampac for their valuable support and assistance for this research.

Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

References

- [1] Chanco, B. (2022, July 4). Crisis in education | Philstar.com. The Philippine Star. <https://www.philstar.com/business/2022/07/04/2192779/crisis-education>
- [2] Gatchalian, W. (2020, September 28). Improve quality of teacher education, training – Win Gatchalian. Win Gatchalian. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <http://wingatchalian.com/news/improve-quality-of-teacher-education-training/>
- [3] Holland's theory. (n.d.). Careers NZ. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://www.careers.govt.nz/resources/career-practice/career-theory-models/hollands-theory/>
- [4] Implementing the Senior High School Support Program. (2022, June 17). Asian Development Bank. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://www.adb.org/projects/48284-001/main>
- [5] IPCRFs for Teacher I - III. (n.d.). TeacherPH. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://www.teacherph.com/ipcrfs-teacher/>

- [6] The K to 12 Basic Education Program. (n.d.). Official Gazette. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/k-12/>
- [7] Mendoza, J. E. (2022, September 27). PH needs 147000 new teachers, hiring 10000 not enough — ACT. Inquirer.net. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1671628/2-ph-needs-147000-new-teachers-hiring-10000-not-enough-act>
- [8] Preparing for International Teaching Certificate - Educational Collaborative for International Schools. (n.d.). ECIS. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://www.ecis.org/pitc/>
- [9] Statistics. (n.d.). CHED. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://ched.gov.ph/statistics/>
- [10] Sueoka, T. (n.d.). Career and Technical Education. Hawaii DOE. Retrieved December 5, 2022, from <https://www.hawaiipublicschools.org/TeachingAndLearning/StudentLearning/CTE/Pages/default.aspx>
- [11] Zunker, V. G. (2016). Career Counseling: A Holistic Approach. Cengage Learning